

CLINICAL SPECTRUM AND MANAGEMENT OF PENILE ABSCESS: CASE SERIES

*Dr. S. Joseph Philipraj, Dr. Ashutosh Kankal

*Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and Research Institute- SBV, Pondicherry- India.

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*Corresponding Author

Dr. S. Joseph Philipraj

Mahatma Gandhi Medical College and
Research Institute- SBV, Pondicherry-
India.

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Penile abscess is a rare urological condition in which a localised collection of pus within penile tissue, commonly in corporal bodies resulting from infection, trauma or iatrogenic causes and in immuno-compromised status which makes it challenging for diagnostic and therapeutic purposes.

Case Presentation: Two cases of male patients 41 yrs and 50 yrs old. Both are known case of Diabetes Mellitus. Presented to Urology OPD with painful swelling over penis and per urethral discharge with fever for 10 days and 7 days respectively. First case was having tender fluctuant swelling of size 3x4 cm over the base of penis. Second case had Painful swelling of size 2x3 cm over ventrolateral aspect of penis. Laboratory results showed leucocytosis. First case was Hepatitis B positive. Both underwent Ultrasound Penis and scrotum. Both underwent Incision and drainage of abscess and

local debridement. **Discussion:** A penile abscess can be caused by a variety of factors. Treatment includes intravenous antibiotics, radiologically guided needle aspiration, or open surgical drainage. **Conclusion:** In addition to antibiotic treatment, surgical debridement is the main stay in the management of penile abscess.

KEYWORDS: Penile abscess, Antibiotics, Surgical drainage.

INTRODUCTION

Penile abscess is a rare entity. It has been linked to erectile dysfunction injection therapy, penile instrumentation, trauma.^[9] Immunocompromised individuals are more susceptible to

develop penile abscess. Idiopathic/spontaneous penile abscess is a known entity.^[10,11] The varied aetiologies of penile abscess are also reflected in the variation of organisms cultured from abscess swabs. Organisms cultured from penile abscesses include the following: *Streptococcus constellatus*, *Streptococcus intermedius*, *Prevotella bivia*, *Streptococcus anginosus*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Escherichia Coli*, *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, and *Staphylococcus aureus* & *Streptococci*^[8], and *Bacteroides*. We hereby present two cases of penile abscess in Diabetic individuals.

CASE PRESENTATION

Case 1

A 41-year-old man presented with history of painful and swollen penis for 10 days. The patient is known case of Diabetes Mellitus and on anti-diabetic medications for 5 years.

Prior to visit to our place patient had a history of fever that did not improve with antibiotics and pain in the penile area. He underwent thorough clinical and radiological examination. On clinical examination tender fluctuant swelling of size 3x4 cm over the base of penis. Ultrasound Penis showed 3.5x3.1x2.1 cm (Vol ~15cc) Collection noted at the base of the penis. Patient was admitted and underwent Surgical exploration of penis with incision and drainage of the collection. Necrotic tissue debrided until bleeding edges. Dorsal slit was performed and dressing done. Patient was managed with Intra venous antibiotics and discharged on Post Operative day 3 with Foleys catheter in situ. Two weeks post-operative follow-up showed a good wound closure, intact, and no blood seepage at the edges of the tissue.

Fig. 1: Pre-operative photos.

Fig. 2: Intra-operative photos.

Case 2

A 50-year-old man was seen in urology OPD with 10 days history of painful and swollen penis and fever on & off. The patient is known case of Diabetes Mellitus and on anti-diabetic medications.

One week before admission, the patient had a history of fever and pain in the penis. The patient then visited to our hospital. He was evaluated thoroughly. He underwent to ultra sound examination of the penis. On clinical examination diffuse tender penile swelling of size

5x3 cm noted on the ventrolateral aspect. Ultrasound Penis showed diffuse multiple hypoechoic foci with dirty shadowing in penile subcutaneous tissue.? Infective aetiology abscess. Patient was admitted. Preoperatively patient found to have Hepatitis B positive. He underwent Surgical exploration of penis with incision and drainage of the collection. Necrotic tissue debrided until bleeding edges. Patient was managed with Intra venous antibiotics and discharged on Post Operative day 10 with Foleys catheter in situ. Two weeks post-operative follow-up showed a good wound closure, intact, and no blood seepage at the edges of the tissue.

Fig. 3: Pre-operative photos.

Fig. 3: Post-Debridement Photo.

Laboratory Parameters

Sr. No.	Parameters	Patient 1	Patient 2
1.	Haemoglobin (g/dl)	11.8	10.9
2.	Total counts(cells/cu.mm)	13200	7700
3.	Random Sugar (mg/dl)	121	134
4.	HbA1c (gm%)	6.0	1409
5.	Serum Creatinine (mg/dl)	1.16	0.98
6.	Urine Culture	Sterile	Sterile
7.	Wound Swab culture	Streptococcus spp	Enterococcus spp

Limitations

Small sample size; as only 2 patients were included in the present study, so findings cannot be generalized.

Strength

Present study highlights a rare clinical condition which helps clinicians to recognize rare pattern, diagnostic pitfalls and management strategies.

DISCUSSION

Penile abscess is an uncommon urological condition that typically manifests as a localized penile swelling and pain. Penile abscess can be caused by a variety of factors, including penile trauma, substance injection into the penis, priapism, penile prosthesis, and disseminated infection. Diabetes, dental caries, and sexually transmitted diseases are regarded as risk factors for penile abscess. There are a significant number of cases of spontaneous penile abscess for which no causative factor has been identified. In our case, patient developed a penile abscess. The penile abscess may be due to uncontrolled blood sugars and

perineal poor hygiene. Two weeks post-operative follow-up as there are no identified factors that could lead to this condition. Ultrasonography of the penis was used for diagnosis. Ultrasonography is a readily accessible method for locating and guiding drainage. In this case, we used ultrasonography to aid in the diagnosis of penile abscess. Penile abscesses may be treated with intravenous anti biotics, radiologically guided needle aspiration, or open surgical drainage. Antibiotic treatment should be based on the microorganism isolated from culture and sensitivity, but it can be started empirically. Open surgical drainage permits complete drainage and rinsing of the abscess, as well as a more thorough examination of the surrounding concomitant pathology. Furthermore, two-stage penile reconstruction using scrotal flap may be performed in some cases of penile abscess. Surgical treatment of penile abscesses may result in a variety of complications. Penile curvature is the most common complication following penile abscess and its surgical treatment. The development of penile fibrosis and curvature after surgical drainage generally does not result in poor erectile function. In contrast, the drainage procedure usually reversed the condition. Although rare, partial erectile dysfunction after abscess drainage after 6-month follow-up has been previously reported. There were no complications found in these cases.

CONCLUSIONS

Though penile abscess is a rare Urological condition but requires high clinical suspicion, prompt diagnosis and surgical intervention and antibiotic coverage will prevent long term complications.

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Ethical approval and consent to participate

Not applicable.

Consent for publication

Informed consent for publication of the patient clinical details and clinical images was obtained from the patients.

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